

Phosphate adsorption-desorption kinetics in some acidic soils

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The kinetics of phosphate (P) sorption/desorption processes belonging to Taxonomic classifications of Aeric Haplaquept, Typic Haplumbrept, Typic Haplustalf and Typic Paleustalf, have been studied. The data are fitted to a modified Freundlich type of kinetic equation and modified Elovich equation to yield P sorption rate coefficients, obtained during sorption and desorption runs, and the Elovich parameters namely C_0 , α , β . The kinetic experiments are conducted at 35° and 45°, representative of average seasonal variation in soil temperature for the given soils.

The resulting phosphate sorption rate coefficient and the Elovich kinetic parameters show significant correlation with oxalate-extractable hydrous oxides of Al and Fe of the given soils. The sorption rate coefficients increase with increase in temperature, in agreements with the simple Arrhenius behaviour. The activation energies for the given phosphate sorption processes range from 10.7 to 80.8 kJ mol⁻¹.

In acid soils phosphorus deficiency is generally related not only to low available P of the soils, but also to their capacity to fix fertilizer P in highly insoluble forms. Phosphate fixation in soil involves both adsorption and precipitation reactions, although the former appears to be dominant over a short reaction period¹⁻³. In acid soils, P adsorption is generally attributed to hydrous oxides of iron and aluminium, particularly in tropical soils with low pH. The availability of the applied P fertilizer for crop uptake is regulated by the P sorption and desorption processes. Thus a better understanding of the P sorption and release characteristics of the experimental soils is necessary for ensuring high P fertilizer use efficiency and efficient crop management practices²⁻⁵.

The present study examines the kinetic aspect of P sorption/desorption processes in some acidic soils. An attempt is also made to identify the soil components that are responsible for given P sorption/desorption behaviour of the soils studied.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 gives the important physicochemical properties of New-Chumpta, Tadong, Raghunathpur and Matimohal soils studied. The soils were moderately to weakly acidic (pH 4.67–6.02), varied widely in clay content (19.5–33.8%) and organic carbon contents (0.13–1.59%) and hence specific surface area (18.2–27.2 m²/g) as well as C.E.C. (7.30–15.1 c mol (p⁺) kg⁻¹). The oxalate extractable Al, i.e. the amorphous Al content was rather high in New-Chumpta soil (15.3 µg/g). The New-Chumpta soil was also high in exchangeable Al (44.2 µg/g). The Raghunathpur soil contained higher amount of free Fe₂O₃ and oxalate-extractable Fe than the remaining three experimental soils. The available P content was low in all the experimental soils (6.2–8.1 mg p/kg).

The kinetic parameter, k_s , of P sorption by the given soils was obtained from the intercept of log x vs log t plots and the given initial concentration of the phosphate solu-

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of soils

Soil sample*	pH (Soil : water, 1 : 2.5)	Organic carbon %	Exchangeable bases cmol(p ⁺) kg ⁻¹		C.E.C. c mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Exchan- geable Al µg/g	Sand %	Silt %	Clay %	Surface area m ² /g	Free Fe ₂ O ₃ %	Reactive Al cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹	Oxalate extractable		Available phosphorus mg P/kg
			Ca ^{II}	Mg ^{II}									Fe µg/g	Al µg/g	
New-Chumpta ^d	4.70	1.59	3.87	0.82	14.0	44.2	61.2	16.4	22.4	27.2	0.85	18.9	3.60	15.3	7.3
Tadong ^b	4.67	1.37	4.22	0.61	15.1	15.4	56.1	10.1	33.8	26.5	1.51	23.0	6.00	0.30	8.1
Raghunathpur ^c	5.94	0.67	4.72	0.70	7.30	39.7	53.2	27.3	19.5	18.2	1.92	10.4	7.08	0.10	6.2
Matimohal ^d	6.02	0.13	3.92	0.91	10.3	29.2	64.7	13.1	22.2	21.0	0.65	6.50	0.47	2.70	6.4

*Taxonomic classification : ^aAeric Haplaquept, ^bTypic Haplumbrept, ^cTypic Haplustalf, ^dTypic Paleustalf.

Fig. 1. Specific phosphate sorption (x) by three representative soils at 35° as a function of time (t) on a logarithmic scale (Δ) Tadong (\circ) New Chumpta (\bullet) Raghunathpur

tion used, a representative plot is presented in Fig 1. The k_a values at 35 and 45° for P sorption are presented in Table 2. The Elovich parameters at 35 and 45° , namely, C_0 , α and β values for the given P sorption process (Table 2), generally corroborated the above trend in that a decrease in β and/or an increase in α leads to enhancement of the P sorption reaction rate (eq 2), in agreement with the earlier observations of Chien and Clayton⁶. These values of α , β and C_0 were obtained graphically in a manner stated in the Experimental section.

Table 2. Phosphate sorption kinetic parameters at 35° and 45°

Soil sample	k_1 , obtaining during		C_0 ppm	α	β
	Sorption	Desorption			
Temp = 35°					
New Chumpta	0.18	0.17	45.0	32.7	0.298
Tadong	0.23	0.18	40.5	37.8	0.254
Raghunathpur	0.08	0.02	48.0	14.5	0.353
Matimohal	0.10	0.06	47.5	29.7	0.301
Temp = 45°					
New Chumpta	0.40	0.38	30.5	21.3	0.311
Tadong	0.48	0.46	26.5	29.7	0.301
Raghunathpur	0.23	0.18	41.0	9.0	0.393
Matimohal	0.29	0.26	27.0	15.7	0.354

A representative plot of C_t against $\ln t$ (eq 4) at 45° is presented in Fig 2. It was observed that k_a values were correlated negatively with β ($r = -0.880$ at 35° and $r = -0.968^{**}$ at 45°) and positively with α ($r = 0.851$ at 35° and $r = 0.988^{**}$ at 45°) for the given soils (Table 2). Further, C_0 being the value of C_t at $t = 0$, it is expected to provide a measure of the maximum P concentration following P application in a soil. In that context, a significant negative correlation between k_a and C_0 ($r = -0.962^{**}$ at 35° and $r = 0.998^{**}$ at 45°) is considered satisfactory. The k_a values for the experimental soils were found to increase with temperature from 35 to $45 \pm 1^\circ$ (Table 3). The corresponding activation energy (ΔE) obtained from the integrated form of the Arrhenius equation, ranged from 74.4 to 108 kJ mol^{-1} (Table 3).

Fig 2. Elovich plots of C_t vs $\ln t$ at 45° (\bullet) Matimohal (Δ) Raghunathpur (\circ) Tadong (\square) New Chumpta

Table 3. Activation energy (ΔE) for phosphate sorption by soils

Soil sample	k_1		ΔE kJ mol^{-1}
	35°	45°	
New Chumpta	0.18	0.40	80.8
Tadong	0.23	0.48	74.4
Raghunathpur	0.08	0.23	10.7
Matimohal	0.10	0.29	10.8

During desorption (Table 2), the k_a values were lower than those during P sorption, due possibly to transformation of sorbed P which rendered it less susceptible to further release⁷.

Linear correlation coefficients were worked out between k_a , α and β on one hand, and various relevant soil properties on the other. The adsorption rate coefficient (k_a) during sorption was positively correlated with organic carbon content (0.808 at 35° and 0.756 at 45°) and oxalate extractable (Fe + Al) ($r = 0.342$ at 35° and $r = 0.306$ at 45°). A positive correlation ($r = 0.756$) was also found between organic carbon and oxalate extractable (Fe + Al) (0.168 at 35° and 0.166 at 45°). The information generated as above may be incorporated into crop management practices while planning for an appropriate P source rate and time of application for the given acid soils.

Experimental

Four acidic surface soil samples (0–0.15 m) were collected from New-Chumpta, Matimohal, Raghunathpur in West Bengal and one soil sample from Tadong (Sikkim). The samples were air-dried after removal of the root residues, then crushed and passed through a 2 mm sieve.

Soil pH was measured in 1 : 1 (w/v) soil-water mixtures using a pH meter. Organic carbon in soil was determined⁸. CEC was obtained by the neutral molar NH_4OAc extraction with exchangeable Ca and Mg in the leachate being

determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Exchangeable Al was determined by the method of 1 M KCl extraction⁹ whereas particle size distribution of the given soils was carried out by following the hydrometer method¹⁰. Surface area of the samples was measured by ethylene glycol retention method¹¹ and free iron oxide by sodium dithionate method¹². Reactive Al was estimated by the reported method¹³, whereas oxalate-extractable Fe and Al were obtained by extraction of soils with 0.3 M ammonium oxalate (pH 3.25)¹⁴. Available phosphorus content of the soils was determined by extraction of soils with Bray-1 extractant¹⁵, and estimating the extracted phosphorus colorimetrically¹⁶.

Phosphate sorption/desorption kinetic experiment : Each soil sample (5 g) was treated in centrifuge tube (100 ml) with 0.01 M KCl solution (50 ml) containing 50 ppm P (in the form of KH_2PO_4). The tubes were shaken for 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0 and 6.0 h in a water-bath shaker at constant temperature (35 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$). At the end of each period, the appropriate samples were extracted and phosphate in the supernatant was determined colorimetrically¹⁶.

Data obtained on P sorbed by unit weight of soil, i.e. specific phosphate sorption (x) and P concentration in solution and time at 35° and 45° were fitted to the modified Freundlich type of kinetic equation¹⁷,

$$x = k_a C_0 t^{1/m} \quad (1)$$

where, C_0 is the initial concentration of P in solution, k_a a constant related to the rate at which the given P sorption system approaches equilibrium, t the time and m a constant.

The Elovich (or the Roginsky-Zeldovich) equation or its modified forms have often been used to treat the kinetics of P adsorption and release in soils and soil minerals^{5,6,18}. The equation has the advantage over a number of kinetic equation proposed to describe the kinetics of phosphate sorption by soils and sediments, in that it does not necessitate (for explaining the experimental data) the postulation of several simultaneous (parallel) reactions to account for the given phosphate sorption processes. The Elovich equation reads,

$$dq/dt = \alpha \exp(-\beta q) \quad (2)$$

which, on transformations and with the assumption of $\alpha\beta t \gg 1$, becomes

$$q = (1/\beta) \ln(\alpha\beta) + (1/\beta) \ln t \quad (3)$$

where, q is the amount adsorbed in time t , and α and β are constants for a given sorption process. α may be regarded as the initial reaction rate because $(dq/dt) \rightarrow \alpha$ as $q \rightarrow 0$, that is, a rapid adsorption rate not governed by the exponential law. Obviously, a decrease in β and/or an increase in α would enhance the reaction rate (eqn. 2). On replacing q in eqn. (3) by $(C_0 - C_t)$, where C_0 and C_t are the P concentrations at the initial time and at any arbitrary time (t), one obtains the modified Elovich equation^{6,19},

$$C_0 - C_t = (1/\beta) \ln(\alpha\beta) + (1/\beta) \ln t \quad (4)$$

The kinetic data from the present P sorption experiment (at 35 and $45 \pm 1^\circ$) were also fitted to eqn. (4). The parameter β was obtained from the negative inverse of the linear plot of C_t against $\ln t$ (eqn. 4). To obtain α from the intercept, knowledge of C_0 was necessary; C_0 was estimated by plotting C_t against t , and then extrapolating to zero time.

For studying the kinetics of P desorption, soils having known amounts of sorbed P at 35 and at 45° in 0.01 M KCl solution, were shaken at the same temperature for the specified time periods. The P concentration in the supernatant was measured at each interval to determine the amount of P desorbed. This was used to compute the amount of P still sorbed by the given soil samples at different times. The data were fitted to modified Freundlich-type of kinetic equation (eqn. 1) to yield the appropriate k_a value during desorption run.

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